

ABSTRACT

This research investigates the influence of tidal interactions between orbiting exoplanets and their host stars on stellar pulsations, presenting an innovative method for exoplanet detection based on variations in these pulsations. Unlike traditional detection techniques, such as radial velocity and the transit method, which are limited by the system's alignment with the observer's line of sight, this study focuses on how tidal forces from exoplanets affect stellar pulsations—an effect that can be used to detect exoplanets without requiring alignment. The key advantage of this approach is its potential to detect exoplanets independently of the alignment constraints that traditional methods face. Photometric data from the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS) mission was employed to analyze exoplanet candidates with stars exhibiting variable pulsations and jovian-like planets. Using the `Period04` and `Pyriod` packages, the pulsation frequencies of the host stars were extracted and examined for harmonic relationships with the orbital frequencies of the exoplanets. The analysis focused on the frequency ratios between the pulsation frequencies of the stars and the orbital frequencies of the exoplanets, along with corresponding amplitude and phase variations, to study the interaction between the star and the planet. This study highlights the potential of detecting exoplanets through tidal-induced variations in stellar pulsations and serves as an initial exploration of tidal pulsation analysis as a new exoplanet detection method. This approach could complement or improve existing detection techniques. Future work can enhance this method through theoretical modeling with `MESA` and `GYRE`, supported by comparisons to observational data for further validation.

Keywords: Tidal interactions, Stellar pulsation, Radial velocity, Transit method, TESS, `Period04`, `Pyriod`.